

NOTES

Conductometric Study of Some Metal Complexes
with Amino Antipyrine

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Complexes of Ni and Co¹, Zn² and Cd³ salts with Amino Antipyrine (Am.Ant.) have been studied gravimetrically. The conductometric titration of mixtures of Am.Ant. with salts of these four metals containing NH₄CNS in stoichiometric amount confirm the ratio in which they form the complexes. Ni gave green, Co pink, Zn and Cd white precipitates. The salts NiSO₄, 6H₂O, CoCl₂ 6H₂O, Zn (CHCOO)₂, Cd(NO₃)₂.4H₂O, and NH₄CNS used were of B.D.H. Analar quality and the reagent Am.Ant. laboratory pure chemical (Fluka). Conductivity water (air free) was used in the experiment and both Job's⁴ method of continuous variation and monovariation method⁵ were adopted. The results are summarised in Tables I and II. In the tables *C* represent the concentration of the metal solution and *P* the ratio *C*'/*C* (*C*' being the concentration of Am.Ant. solution).

TABLE I

Mono-Variation method (Direct and Reverse Titration)

Salts	<i>C</i> × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>	<i>C</i> ' × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>	Metal : Am.Ant.
			at the inflection
NiSO ₄	5.00	10.00	1 : 2
and	10.00	20.00	1 : 2
NH ₄ CNS	10.00	10.00	1 : 2
CoCl ₂	10.00	10.00	1 : 2
and	6.66	6.66	1 : 2
NH ₄ CNS	5.00	10.00	1 : 2
Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂	20.00	20.00	1 : 2
and	10.00	10.00	1 : 2
NH ₄ CNS	10.00	20.00	1 : 2
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	10.00	10.00	1 : 2
and	5.00	5.00	1 : 2
NH ₄ CNS	4.00	8.00	1 : 2

1. J. Dick and C. Drugarin, *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 59, 6201f.2, 3. J. Dick and A. Maurer, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 61, 5182f; 1963, 59, 2366e.4. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, X, 9, 113.5. Nayar and Pande, *Proc. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284.

TABLE II

Job's Method (Equimolar and Non-equimolar)

Salts	$C \times 10^{-2} M$	P	Vol. at the peak	Composition of the complex	Total Vol. ml.
NiSO ₄	10.00	1	4	1 : 2	15
and	8.00	1	4	1 : 2	15
NH ₄ CNS	6.66	1	4	1 : 2	15
	10.00	2	6	1 : 2	15
	8.00	2	6	1 : 2	15
	6.66	2	6	1 : 2	15
CoCl ₂	4.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
and	3.33	1	4	1 : 2	12
NH ₄ CNS	2.5	1	4	1 : 2	12
	2.5	2	6	1 : 2	12
	1.66	2	6	1 : 2	12
Zn(CH ₃ COO) ₂	6.66	1	4	1 : 2	12
and	4.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
NH ₄ CNS	5.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
	2.00	2	5	1 : 2	10
	2.00	2.5	5	1 : 2	09
	1.66	2	6	1 : 2	12
Cd(NO ₃) ₂	2.00	1	4	1 : 2	12
and	1.66	1	4	1 : 2	12
NH ₄ CNS	2.50	1	4	1 : 2	12
	1.66	2	6	1 : 2	12
	2.50	2	6	1 : 2	12
	2.00	1.66	5	1 : 2	11

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